

Methods for Solving a Problem Involving Fractional Algebraic Equations

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Abstract: In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we solve a problem involving fractional algebraic equations. The solutions of this problem can be obtained by using some methods. In fact, our results are generalizations of the results of ordinary algebraic equations.

Keywords: New multiplication, Fractional analytic functions, Fractional algebraic equations.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the development of science and technology, especially since the 20th century, the theory and application of fractional calculus began to be widely concerned. Fractional calculus has been used in the research of physics, mechanics, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, biology, economics, and other fields [1-11].

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we study a problem involving fractional algebraic equations. Using some techniques, we can solve this problem. On the other hand, our results are generalizations of the results of traditional algebraic equations.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1 ([12]): Let x and a_k be real numbers for all k , and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha}$, then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic function.

Next, a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions is introduced.

Definition 2.2 ([13]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Suppose that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes k}, \quad (1)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes k}. \quad (2)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} \otimes \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} a_{k-m} b_m \right) x^{k\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Equivalently,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes k} \otimes \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes k} \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} a_{k-m} b_m\right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes k}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Definition 2.3 ([14]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is a α -fractional analytic functions. Then $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes n} = f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes \dots \otimes f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the n th power of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we solve a problem involving fractional algebraic equations by using some methods.

Problem 3.1: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x, y be real numbers, $x^\alpha \neq y^\alpha$. If the following α -fractional algebraic equations hold:

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1, \tag{5}$$

and

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1. \tag{6}$$

Find

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes n} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha\right]^{\otimes n}, \tag{7}$$

for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 6$.

Solution Since $\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha$ and $\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha$ satisfy the α -fractional algebraic equation

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha + 1. \tag{8}$$

That is, x^α and y^α are two distinct solutions of the following 2nd order algebraic equation

$$\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} t^{2\alpha} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha - 1 = 0. \tag{9}$$

Therefore,

$$x^\alpha + y^\alpha = -\frac{\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}}{\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}} = \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, \tag{10}$$

Hence,

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha = \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2}. \tag{11}$$

Furthermore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1 \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2.
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

In addition,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 3} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 3} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1\right] + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1\right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 + \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2.
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 4} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 4} \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right] \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right] + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1 \right] \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1 \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + 2 \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right] + 2 \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 + 2 \cdot \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 \\
 &= \frac{3 \cdot \Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 4.
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 5} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 5} \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right] \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right] \otimes \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1 \right] \otimes \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1 \right] \otimes \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + 2 \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \right] + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right] \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 + 2 \left[\frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 \right] + \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} \\
 &= \frac{5 \cdot \Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 6.
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 6} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 6} \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right]^{\otimes 3} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha + 1 \right]^{\otimes 3} \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + 3 \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \right] + 3 \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} y^\alpha \right] + 2 \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 + 3 \left[\frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 2 \right] + 3 \left[\frac{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} \right] + 2 \\
 &= \frac{4 \cdot \Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2} + 10.
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we solve a problem involving fractional algebraic equations. In fact, the fractional algebraic equation is a generalization of ordinary algebraic equation. We can solve this problem by using some methods. In the future, we will continue to use the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to solve the problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

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